

Impacts of Social Media Engagements and Perceived Academic Distraction among Undergraduates in University of Ibadan

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Abstract

Huge dependence on internet enabled devices such as laptop computers and smartphones have been found to be a source of academic distraction among students in universities. Therefore, this study investigated social media engagements and perceived academic distractions among undergraduates in the University of Ibadan. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The study was carried out in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria. Eight faculties were randomly selected from the University and a simple random technique was used to select a total of 50 student each from the selected faculties. Three hundred and eighty-one bachelor's degree students participated in the study. One self-constructed instrument named: Undergraduates Social Media Engagement and Perceived Academic Distraction Questionnaire (USMEPADQ) was used for data collection after the reliability (.92) had been determined. Data collected were descriptively analysed using frequency count, percentage score, mean and standard deviation. The decision rule was placed at 2.50. It was recommended that university management in conjunction with lecturers or instructors together with the students should come up with classroom technology policies in order to protect the integrity of the learning environments.

Keywords: social media, Social media Engagement, Undergraduates Academic Distraction, University of Ibadan.

Introduction

With the advent and integration of technological devices to facilitate instruction for improved outcomes, teaching and learning have recently assumed a new dimension. For instance, contemporary educational institutions utilize internet-enabled devices in the classroom, including smartphones, laptops, tablets, and so forth, to facilitate a wide range of academic and experiential assignments. According to Prescott et al. (2012), it is typical to incorporate electronic devices into one's daily life, including laptop computers, smartphones, and tablets. Additionally, they noted that mobile devices are among the electronic devices utilized to facilitate the teaching and learning process.

Academic diversion has emerged as a consequence of the widespread adoption of smartphones and other technological devices among university students. As the learning environment continues to evolve as a result of a heightened reliance on technology, technological devices, and the internet in and out of the classroom, educators are becoming increasingly troubled (Dontre, 2021). University students' excessive reliance on internet-enabled devices, including smartphones and laptops, has been identified as a source of academic distraction (Attia et al., 2017).

Academic distraction can be succinctly defined as the incapability of students to devote the necessary time, attention, and focus to their studies while attending lectures in the classroom or when they are expected to independently study for their academic program outside of class. Academic distraction is an intrinsic and extrinsic factor that hinders students' ability to complete academic tasks with accuracy and precision, according to Feng et al. (2019). Students' academic achievement is significantly predicted by academic distraction (Gol et al., 2023).

The potential distractions caused by the extensive use of technology in college instruction and learning have been noted by Gol et al. (2023). According to a study by Graham and Salberg (2020), the utilization of digital technologies and the active participation of students on social media platforms resulted in a decline in students' ability to concentrate on learning tasks and an increase in distractions. More than seventy-five percent of students who use social media on their laptop computers experience academic distraction, according to Douglas et al. (2012).

A study conducted by Chen et al. (2014) during 2012-2013 involved 1,150 students selected from six universities located in Africa, the United States, and China. An association was found between the amount of time college students spent on the internet, addiction to social media and the internet, gender, age, and addiction with academic distraction. Patil et al. (2019) discovered that students required more time to complete projects and turn in assignments when they spent time on the internet engaging in unrelated activities. Such activities consist of time spent interacting on social media platforms, chatting via phone applications, and playing video games.

Social media refer to online platforms and websites where users register in order to communicate, share visual content such as pictures, voice notes, short videos, and other graphics, and interact with one another. It serves as a medium for individuals of various backgrounds to exchange viewpoints, interests, and engage in discussions pertaining to urgent societal matters (Swar and Hameed, 2017). Media engagement on social media platforms pertains to the extent to which an individual dedicates time and participates in activities related to disseminating personal viewpoints, information, videos, and other content to various individuals—including family members, friends, and even unidentified followers (Alt, 2015; Swar and Hameed, 2017). According to the findings of Salehan and Negahban (2013), Jeong et al. (2016), Swar and Hameed (2017), college students who devote a great deal of time to social media are prone to developing an addiction to their internet-enabled devices, including smartphones, laptops, and tablets. This addiction is a significant predictor of academic distraction. Research has established a negative correlation between the amount of time students spend on social media and their academic achievement. Rosen et al. (2013) discovered that the GPAs of students who utilized social media actively were lower than those who did not.

From the foregoing, researchers have found that excessive use of internet enabled devices by undergraduates can reduce the amount of time spent on academic activities in and out of class. Similarly, social media engagements which are a by product of distraction through internet enabled devices have a negative relationship with students' academic performance. Somehow,

while these findings have focused on the implications of digital devices and social media engagements on student's learning outcomes, sufficient attention has not been given to what the undergraduates perceive as the implications of social media engagements on their academic ability. This is important to determine whether undergraduates' perception of the implications of social media engagement aligns what the outcomes of past findings in this area. Therefore, this study investigated social media engagements and perceived academic distractions among undergraduates in the University of Ibadan.

Research questions

1. What is the frequency of social media engagement among undergraduates in the University of Ibadan?
2. What is the perception of undergraduates' social media engagements on distractions experienced in their academics?

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The study was carried out in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria. Eight faculties were randomly selected from the University and a simple random technique was used to select 50 student each from the selected faculties. Three hundred and eighty-one bachelor degree students participated in the study. One self-constructed instrument named: "Undergraduates Social Media Engagement and Perceived Academic Distraction Questionnaire (USMEPADQ)" was used to collect data in the study. The instrument has three (3) sections. Section A with 5 items collects demographic information of respondents; Section B has 10 items: it collects the frequency of undergraduates' social media engagement. Section C has 10 items, and it collects information on undergraduates' perception of social media engagements and distractions experienced in their academics. Section B was structured on a four-point scale of Always (A), Sometimes (S), Rarely (R) and Never (N). and C were structured on a four-point scale of Always (A), Sometimes (S), Rarely (R) and Never (N). Positive items were scored as 4, 3, 2 and 1, while negatively worded items were scored 1, 2, 3, and 4 respectively. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by experts in the Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan while the reliability was

determined by administering limited number of the instrument (50) to a separate sample who did not participate in the study. The data collected during the pilot dissemination for reliability was subjected to item-by-item analysis using Cronbach Alpha; the instrument yielded the co-efficient of .92. The data collected from the study were descriptively analysed using frequency counts, percentage scores, mean, standard deviation and tables.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the frequency of social media engagement among undergraduates in the University of Ibadan?

Table 1: Frequency of Social Media Engagement among Undergraduates in the University of Ibadan

S/N	ITEM	All the time	Often	Rarely	Never	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	My Internet Enabled Devices (IED) such as smartphones, tablets, laptops, etc. always have internet connection.	154 (40.4)	181 (47.5)	31 (8.1)	15 (3.9)	3.24	0.76
2	I access my social media accounts through my IEDs such as smartphones, tablets, laptops, etc.	132 (34.6)	113 (29.7)	103 (27)	33 (8.7)	2.90	0.97
3	My social media applications are always on and running even when I am in class attending lectures	158 (41.5)	90 (23.6)	79 (20.7)	54 (14.2)	2.92	1.08
4	My social media applications are on and running during my personal time of study in the library, at home, etc.	55 (14.4)	85 (22.3)	164 (43)	77 (20.2)	2.31	0.95
5	My social media applications are up when I am having group discussions or interactions with colleagues or other students.	100 (26.2)	132 (34.6)	98 (25.7)	51 (13.4)	2.74	0.99
6	I check my social media accounts first thing every morning before active days' work	123 (32.3)	171 (44.9)	73 (19.2)	14 (3.7)	3.06	0.81
7	During the day, I keep tab on my social media accounts to stay in touch with latest happenings, gists, conversations, trending issues, etc.	121 (31.8)	155 (40.7)	89 (23.4)	16 (4.2)	3.00	0.84

8	My social media accounts are the last thing I check in the night before going to bed.	140 (36.7)	152 (39.9)	56 (14.7)	33 (8.7)	3.05	0.92
9	I am always on social media because of the need to stay close with family and friends	143 (37.5)	155 (40.7)	64 (16.8)	17 (4.5)	3.13	0.85
10	I am always on social media because of the need to get entertained with videos, images, comments, etc.	148 (38.8)	175 (45.9)	48 (12.6)	10 (2.6)	3.21	0.76
Weighted mean = 2.96; Threshold = 2.50							

Table 1 indicate a weighted mean of 2.96 which is greater than the threshold set at 2.50. This implies that social media engagement among undergraduates in the University of Ibadan is very high. Nine of the ten items used in the questionnaire contributed positively to undergraduate’s social media engagement. In the order of magnitude, the items are: item 1, which shows that undergraduates in the University of Ibadan have internet, enabled devices that is always connected to the internet (mean 3.24 > 2.50). Item 10 – which shows that undergraduates are always on the social media because of the need to get entertained with videos, images, comments and so on (3.21 > 2.50). item 9 - I am always on social media because of the need to stay close with family and friends (mean = 3.13 > 2.50). Item 6 - I check my social media accounts first thing every morning before active days’ work (mean = 3.06 > 2.50).

Item 8 - My social media accounts are the last thing I check in the night before going to bed. (mean =3.05 > 2.50). Item 7 - During the day, I keep tab on my social media accounts to stay in touch with latest happenings, gists, conversations, trending issues, and so on (mean = 3.00 > 2.50). Item 3 - My social media applications are always on and running even when I am in class attending lectures (mean =2.92 > 2.50). Item 2 - I access my social media accounts through my IEDs such as smartphones, tablets, laptops, etc. (mean = 2.90 > 2.50). Lastly, item 5 - My social media applications are up when I am having group discussions or interactions with colleagues or other students. (mean = 2.74 > 2.50).

Research Question 2: What is the perception of undergraduates’ social media engagements on distractions experienced in their academics?

Table 2: Perception of undergraduates’ Social Media Engagement and Academic Distractions

S/N	ITEM	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	I do read or reply to pop-up messages from my social media accounts when in the classroom receiving lectures	48 (12.6)	108 (28.3)	122 (32)	103 (27)	1.27	0.99
2	I do read, reply and engage in one-on-one/group chatting on the social media during my personal time of academic study.	200 (52.5)	96 (25.2)	58 (15.2)	27 (7.1)	2.23	0.95
3	I do read, reply and chat during group discussion/projects or assignments.	177 (46.5)	88 (23.1)	76 (19.9)	40 (10.5)	2.06	1.04
4	Students that do not chat on social media or are engaged with social media during lectures are likely to perform better academically than students who do.	158 (41.5)	90 (23.6)	86 (22.6)	47 (12.3)	1.94	1.06
5	Reading, chatting or replying to messages on social media during lectures can make a student to lose concentration of what is being taught in class	56 (14.7)	47 (12.3)	60 (15.7)	218 (57.2)	0.85	1.12
6	Reading, chatting or replying to messages on social media during private time of study can make a student to loose interest in studying.	167 (43.8)	99 (26)	75 (19.7)	40 (10.5)	2.03	1.02
7	Many times, I have failed to meet up with deadlines to turn in assignments or projects or class work due to social media engagements	221 (58)	79 (20.7)	49 (12.9)	32 (8.4)	2.28	0.98
8	I will have more time to attend to my academic work if I spend less time on the social media.	171 (44.9)	67 (17.6)	76 (19.9)	67 (17.6)	1.90	1.16
9	I will have more time to prepare for tests and examinations if I spend less time on the social media.	103 (27)	93 (24.4)	73 (19.2)	112 (29.4)	1.49	1.17
10	Cumulatively, I believe my GPA will improve significantly if I dedicate more time to my study and less time to the social media.	193 (50.7)	62 (16.3)	80 (21)	46 (12.1)	2.06	1.09
Weighted mean = 1.81; Threshold = 2.50							

Table 2 presents perception of undergraduates' social media engagement and academic distractions in the University of Ibadan. The result yielded the weighted mean of 1.81, which is lower than the established threshold of 2.50. This implies that undergraduates in the University of Ibadan do not perceive that their involvement, activities or staying active on the social media negatively distract them from their academic activities.

Discussions

Findings showed that social media engagement among undergraduates in the University of Ibadan is very high. The trend of this result is not surprising as this finding aligns with previous findings by past similar studies. For example, Eduljee et al. (2022) found that more than 94% of college students have their IEDs near them while in class or having private academic study. The findings in this present study showed that 87.9% of the students have access to devices that are internet enabled, more than half 64.3% use their smart devices to access the social media and 61.5% always have their social media application on even when attending lectures.

The findings are similar to McCoy (2016) who found that college students are 4 – 10 times more likely to remain connected to their digital devices in the classroom. Attia et al. (2017) explained that there is a rise of negative trends of students' distraction through technological devices in colleges, which has made some universities to ban the use of smart devices during classroom lectures. Furthermore, Attia et al. (2017) noted that students' attention is affected in the classroom as many are easily distracted to respond to messages instantly even when academic activities are ongoing. This submission confirms the finding in this present study as more than 65.1% of the students always have their social media applications on and running during times of classroom lectures.

Finding in this present study showed that undergraduates in the University of Ibadan do not perceive that social media engagement could be a source of academic distraction. Amazingly, this finding is not in agreement with many past findings in this area. Kirschner and Karpinski (2010) discovered, for instance, that students who utilize social media have lower GPAs and devote fewer hours per week to studying compared to those who do not. Additionally, Madhdiun et al. (2020) While researchers such as Mehmood and Taswir (2013) discovered that undergraduates utilize social media networks for educational or scientific objectives, including information gathering and professional prospect exploration, certain students regarded social media usage as a source of diversion and experienced discontentment (Madhdiun et al., 2020).

Feng et al. (2019) conducted a study to examine the influence of the internet and Facebook on the academic distraction of college students. The researchers discovered a negative correlation between the utilization of these platforms and the occurrence of academic distraction among students. They reported that students whose primary use of social media was for entertainment purposes, particularly Facebook, were more susceptible to academic distractions and had lower

GPA's. This discovery is supported by the research conducted by Graham and Sahlberg (2020), which indicates that students who are heavily involved in social media activities are less likely to concentrate on their academic assignments. Additionally, Douglas (2012) discovered that academic distractions are more prevalent among students who utilize social media compared to those who do not. Chen et al. (2014) established a correlation between the amount of time spent on social media and academic distractions. Lastly, Gol et al. (2023) argued that excessive utilization of internet-enabled devices may result in distracting outcomes.

Flanigan et al. (2023) maintained that undergraduates who come to class with their IEDs often use them for non-academic purposes, which can hinder and distract their learning and distract the learning of other students sitting close to them.

While past studies have established that there is a relationship between social media and internet engagement and academic distractions among college students, Paasek and Hargittai (2009), Al Rahmi et al. (2014) and Mahdiuon et al. (2020) submitted that social media positively and significantly influenced college students' academic performance if they are meaningfully and intentionally engaged for learning purposes.

Conclusion

Several studies have looked at the influence of social media on academic performance or achievement of university students with specific focus on students learning outcomes while specific attention has not been paid to the perception of university students' social media engagement and their perception of the academic distraction. Therefore, this study investigated social media engagements and perceived academic distractions among undergraduates in the University of Ibadan. The study found that social media engagement among undergraduates in the University of Ibadan is very high. Moreover, undergraduates in the University of Ibadan did not perceive that social media engagement negatively affect their academic activities. The findings aligns with past studies that social media usage among undergraduates has potential to reduce students' capability to focus on learning tasks thereby reducing their learning outcomes. It was recommended that universities should develop a classroom technology policy with the input of lecturers and students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Going by the prevailing use and proliferation of IEDs in classrooms in tertiary institutions, university management in conjunction with lecturers or instructors together with the students need to come up with classroom technology policies in order to protect the integrity of the learning environments. These classroom technology policies will be such that has the input of the students. It should not be imposed.
2. University lecturers or instructors should always engage active learning strategies to reduce students' distractions with IEDs and in order to sustain students' attention. Lecturers or university instructors should guide against reactive measures (such as verbal abuse/reprimand, confiscation, etc.) in curbing technological distractions in their classrooms.
3. Universities should conduct regular orientation programmes in form of seminars on the harmful impacts of excessive social media engagement and internet enabled devices on students' learning outcomes.
4. Universities should define what constitutes appropriate and inappropriate technology use within and outside of the classrooms.

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